

Development of MC/MOC two step method for small and micro nuclear reactor core analysis

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ABSTRACT

Small and micro modular reactors (SMRs and MMRs) feature compact cores with strong spatial heterogeneity and spectrum complexity, posing challenges to conventional diffusion-based homogenization. To address this, a high-fidelity two-step MC/MOC method is developed by combining continuous-energy Monte Carlo (MC)-based multigroup cross-section (MGXS) generation with a fully three-dimensional Method of Characteristics (3D MOC) core transport solver. The MC stage supports three MGXS generation schemes—flux-volume (FV), superhomogenisation (SPH), and a newly implemented transport-corrected flux-moment homogenization (TC-MHT) method—to rigorously treat angular anisotropy of scattering. The resulting MGXS are verified in representative reactor systems, including PWR, GCR, LFR, and SFR cores, demonstrating that SPH and TC-MHT methods significantly reduce reactivity and power biases compared to conventional FV homogenization. To enhance computational efficiency, a multi-objective genetic algorithm (GA) is applied to optimize MOC parameters, yielding Pareto-optimal configurations that balance accuracy and cost. Furthermore, GPU acceleration achieves speedups exceeding two orders of magnitude compared to single-threaded CPUs, enabling practical full-core 3D MOC simulations of small reactors on a single workstation. The proposed MC/MOC framework is extended to multi-physics coupling, including 3D MOC-CTF integration for helical cruciform fuel (HCF) assemblies and MOC/MOOSE coupling for gas-cooled microreactors, achieving high-fidelity power-temperature field prediction. This study establishes an efficient and accurate methodology for next-generation small and micro reactor analysis, bridging MC precision with deterministic scalability.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Method of Characteristics, Multigroup Cross Section, Small Modular Reactor, Multiphysics Coupling, GPU Acceleration

1. INTRODUCTION

Small modular reactors (SMRs) and micro-reactors have compact cores with pronounced heterogeneities and steep flux gradients, which can challenge traditional homogenized diffusion methods. A high-fidelity two-step scheme can address this by using continuous-energy Monte Carlo (MC) to generate multigroup cross-sections (MGXS) for a deterministic core transport solver. MC inherently provides full geometry fidelity and continuous energy resolution without flux approximations, and modern high-performance computing now makes such Monte Carlo-based cross-section generation practical especially for small reactors.

For the core transport calculation, the method of characteristics (MOC) offers a deterministic solver with excellent geometric flexibility and high accuracy. While MOC has traditionally been applied in two-dimensional (radial) plane calculations with axial leakage approximations, a fully three-dimensional MOC can capture complex spatial heterogeneity without 2D/1D coupling assumptions. Full-core 3D MOC simulations have recently been achieved on modern computing clusters, demonstrating improved fidelity for small reactor cores at the expense of greater computational cost.

Integrating MC-generated cross sections with a 3D MOC solver entails several challenges. One key issue is MGXS anisotropy: standard homogenization often discards angular dependence, whereas actual multigroup scattering and total cross sections can vary with neutron direction. Preserving this

information (e.g., via transport-corrected flux-moment homogenization) is critical for accuracy. Another challenge is computational efficiency—both MC and 3D MOC are resource-intensive, so the combined workflow must be optimized. Finally, multi-physics coupling adds complexity, requiring integration of neutronics with thermal-hydraulics (e.g., linking the core solver with a subchannel code) via frameworks like MOOSE.

In this work, an MC/MOC two-step method is developed to tackle these issues. Section 2.1 introduces three MGXS generation techniques: a conventional flat-volume homogenization, the use of superhomogénéisation (SPH) factors to correct homogenization errors, and a novel transport-corrected flux-moment homogenization (TC-MHT) method for handling cross-section anisotropy. Section 2.2 describes improvements to the 3D MOC solver, including a GA-based multi-objective optimization of MOC parameters and the incorporation of GPU acceleration. Section 2.3 presents the coupling of the neutronic solver with the subchannel thermal-hydraulics code and its integration into the MOOSE multi-physics framework.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1. MGXS Generation Method Based on Continuous Energy Monte-Carlo

This section presents MC-based MGXS tailored for 3D MOC core calculations, which require P0 cross sections. We start from the FV baseline (reaction-rate/flux tallies), then incorporate transport correction and flux-moment homogenization (MHT/consistent-P) to embed incident/outgoing anisotropy into the P0 set; SPH is included as an engineering alternative for reaction-rate preservation. The resulting MGXS are assessed in MOC against MC references across multiple cores.

2.1.1. Flux-volume homogenization method

The generation of multigroup cross sections (MGXS) has been extensively developed in various Monte Carlo (MC) codes, including SERPENT^[1], MCNP6^[2], McCARD^[3], RMC^[4], OpenMC^[5], MCS^[6,7] and MCX^[8]. Among these implementations, the flux-volume (FV) homogenization method is the most widely adopted approach.

The macroscopic cross-section of nuclide 'i' within spatial region 'k' and energy range [E_{g-1}, E_g], is defined as the ratio between the group-wise reaction rate $\langle \Sigma_{x,i}, \psi \rangle_{k,g}$ and the corresponding flux $\langle \psi \rangle_{k,g}$, both tallied using track-length estimators in OpenMC:

$$\Sigma_{x,i,k,g} = \frac{\langle \Sigma_{x,i}, \phi \rangle_{k,g}}{\langle \phi \rangle_{k,g}} \quad (1)$$

$$\langle \Sigma_{x,i}, \phi \rangle_{k,g} = \int_{\mathbf{r} \in V_k} d\mathbf{r} \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \Sigma_x(\mathbf{r}, E) \psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \Omega) \quad (2)$$

$$\langle \phi \rangle_{k,g} = \int_{\mathbf{r} \in V_k} d\mathbf{r} \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \Omega) \quad (3)$$

Although the FV homogenization method is conceptually similar across different MC codes, subtle variations exist in the treatment of scattering moments, transport corrections, and energy condensation procedures. Nevertheless, the underlying principle remains consistent: reaction-rate tallies normalized by scalar flux tallies provide the foundation for MGXS generation based on the flux-volume homogenization method.

2.1.2. Superhomogénéisation equivalent techniques

The superhomogénéisation equivalent techniques (SPH)^[9,10] are widely employed to ensure reaction-rate preservation between a reference heterogeneous model and its corresponding homogenized model. The core idea of SPH is to correct the homogenized cross sections in such a way that the homogenized (nodal or cell-averaged) flux reproduces the same reaction rates as the detailed heterogeneous solution. In several studies ^[11,6,7,12,13], SPH techniques have been applied by coupling Monte Carlo-based MGXS generation with nodal diffusion solvers to enhance the accuracy of control rod representation and core-

level homogenization. The detailed methodology can be found in [12]. The SPH technique is characterized by a fixed-point iterative correction that allows the preservation of reaction rates for specific geometrical and material configurations, while requiring the cross-section and flux tallies from the heterogeneous model to be generated only once.

2.1.3. Transport-corrected flux-moment homogenization method

In most MOC core calculations, isotropic (P0) cross sections are required. However, the original scattering behavior in fast reactors is inherently anisotropic. To reconcile this, the transport correction (TC) is commonly applied, which compresses the higher-order Legendre scattering information into the zeroth-order term. This correction effectively accounts for the anisotropy of the outgoing neutron scattering, while maintaining computational compatibility with transport solvers.

Nevertheless, the anisotropy with respect to the incident neutron direction is not captured by the transport correction alone. To address this limitation, the 'consistent-P' approximation was introduced, which modifies the cross sections to preserve consistency between angular flux and scattering source representations. References [14] and [15] extended the original formulation of the consistent-P approximation to two-dimensional and three-dimensional fast reactor analyses, leading to the development of the flux-moment homogenization technique (MHT).

Vidal et al. further proposed a least-squares collapsing method that collapses spherical harmonic flux moments obtained from Monte Carlo simulations into corresponding Legendre moments for deterministic solvers[15]. This MHT framework has since been implemented in OpenMC [16], enabling accurate incorporation of incident-angle anisotropy into the homogenized scattering matrices.

For three-dimensional MOC applications, the required P0 cross sections must incorporate anisotropic effects in both the incoming and outgoing neutron directions. In our previous work [17], we proposed the combined application of the transport correction and flux-moment homogenization technique (TC-MHT) to achieve this goal. The corresponding TC-MHT correction formulation is expressed in Eq. (4-6), ensuring that both anisotropy effects are consistently embedded in the isotropic scattering representation used for 3D MOC analyses.

$$\Sigma_{TC-MHT,g}(r) = \Sigma_{t,g}(r) - \Delta\Sigma_{TC-MHT,g}(r) \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{s,g' \rightarrow g}(r) = \Sigma_{s,0,g' \rightarrow g}(r) - \Delta\Sigma_{TC-MHT,g}(r)\delta(g' - g) \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\Delta\Sigma_{TC-MHT,g}(r) = \frac{\sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,1,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'}(r)}{\phi_g(r)} - \frac{\sum_{m=-l}^l \phi_{l,m,g}(r) R_{t,l,m,g}(r)}{\sum_{m=-l}^l \phi_{l,m,g}(r)^2} + \Sigma_{t,g}(r) \quad (6)$$

2.1.4. MC/MOC two step calculation results and discussion

Table I summarizes the reactivity and pin-wise power distribution errors obtained using different MGXS generation methods for representative reactor systems from our previous and ongoing works. The reported discrepancies correspond to the deviation between the MC/MOC two-step calculation and the Monte Carlo reference calculation, providing a consistent benchmark for assessing homogenization accuracy.

Overall, NuScale, MGCR, and SVBR reactors already exhibit satisfactory agreement with the reference when the conventional flux-volume (FV) homogenization method is applied. Their relatively simple spectral characteristics and moderate spatial heterogeneity allow the FV method to capture the essential reaction-rate behavior with acceptable precision. In contrast, NETH-175, SMSFR, and MegaPower reactors present more challenging configurations, where the FV-based MGXS method fails to maintain sufficient accuracy due to strong spectral gradients and structural anisotropy.

For the NETH-175 pressurized water reactor, applying the SPH correction markedly improves the accuracy of few-group calculations. The reactivity bias is reduced from -377 pcm to $+209$ pcm, and the RMS power deviation decreases from 0.492% to 0.207% . This demonstrates the capability of SPH to compensate for homogenization errors through reaction-rate preservation between heterogeneous and homogenized models.

For the fast-spectrum SMSFR and heterogeneous MegaPower cores, the combined transport-correction and flux-moment homogenization (TC-MHT) method provides a significant accuracy enhancement. In SMSFR, the reactivity bias decreases from 500 pcm to 118 pcm, and the RMS power deviation improves from 1.48% to 0.95% . Similarly, for the fast and thermal versions of the MegaPower design, the TC-MHT method consistently reduces both reactivity and power biases, confirming its effectiveness in capturing the anisotropic scattering characteristic of fast-spectrum systems.

From an overall perspective, both SPH and TC-MHT corrections achieve comparable accuracy improvements in terms of reactivity and pin-by-pin power distribution. However, there is no universal correlation between the reactor type (size, spectrum, or group structure) and the optimal MGXS generation approach. The SPH technique remains a robust and engineering-oriented correction method applicable to a wide range of reactors, though it requires substantial computational resources to generate reactor-specific SPH factors. In contrast, the TC-MHT method is derived directly from the Boltzmann transport equation and theoretically provides a more rigorous treatment of angular anisotropy, yet its applicability to thermal reactors appears limited. Further mechanistic analysis is therefore needed to establish a unified theoretical framework guiding MGXS generation for diverse reactor types.

Table I. Accuracy of MC/MOC scheme for different reactors

Reactor	Power (MWth)	Type	Fuel	MGXS method	Group structure	Reactivity bias (pcm)	RMS power bias (%)	Max power bias (%)
NuScale ^[18]	160	PWR	UOX	FV	CASMO-4	40	1.97	5.35
MGCR ^[19]	15	GCR	FCM	FV	CASMO-25	-298	1.2	4
NETH-175 ^[20]	175	PWR	UZr	FV	CASMO-4	-377	0.492	1.353
				SPH	CASMO-4	209	0.207	0.557
SVBR	280	LFR	UOX	FV	ECCO-24	19	N/A	N/A
SMSFR	300	SFR	MOX	FV	ECCO-24	500	1.48	4.88
				TC-MHT	ECCO-24	118	0.95	4.98
MegaPower -Fast ^[17]	15	HPR	UOX	FV	ECCO-33	765	0.37	2.61
				TC-MHT	ECCO-33	132	0.36	1.79
MegaPower -Thermal ^[17]	15	HPR	UOX	FV	ECCO-33	358	0.77	3.81
				TC-MHT	ECCO-33	152	0.74	3.43

2.2. Improvement of Computational Efficiency

2.2.1. Optimization of MOC parameters

MOC is a method with high numerical accuracy and geometric adaptability, yet it is computationally intensive. Given that MOC parameters exert a notable influence on both computational precision and efficiency, the optimization and selection of MOC parameters are essential. This optimization task poses challenges, primarily because of the large parameter count involved, the nonlinear relationships between parameters and objectives, and the conflicting nature of different objectives. To solve this problem, the genetic algorithm was employed to achieve an intelligent and automated optimization

workflow. The findings confirmed its effectiveness in generating the Pareto front (PF) for MOC, which balances computational accuracy and efficiency.

Figure 1. (a) Flowchart of the optimization; (b) Optimization process of objective value.

2.2.2. GPU-accelerated 3D MOC

3D MOC is computationally intensive. However, its solving process is suitable for parallel computing. GPUs possess powerful floating-point operations and parallel computing capabilities, and thus hold potential for accelerating 3D MOC. Therefore, to further improve computational efficiency, a series of methods for GPU-accelerated 3D MOC computation were implemented to reduce the memory usage. These efforts have enabled efficient full-core calculations of small reactors on a single RTX 4090 GPU. Finally, compared with the single-threaded CPU (AMD EPYC™ 7763), speedups of 193.1, 274.1, and 378.9 were achieved in the C5G7-3D, NuScale, and NETH-HCF175M simulations, respectively. With GPU method, the computation time used for C5G7-3D, NuScale, and NETH-HCF175M are respectively 43, 727 and 802 second, respectively.

Figure 2. (a) Flowchart of GPU-accelerated 3D MOC; (b) The computational performance of CPU and GPU in different cases.

2.3. Multiphysics Analysis

2.3.1. Coupling with RESTAR-HF

Helical cruciform fuel (HCF) presents significant potential for improving reactor economics and safety; however, its complex radial and axial configurations also present challenges for coupled analysis. To solve this problem, neutronics/thermal-hydraulic coupled analysis method of HCF assemblies is implemented using the 3D MOC and the refined subchannel code RESTAR-HF, aiming to address the complex geometry of HCF. Benefiting from the accurate simulations of HCF by both the neutronics and thermal-hydraulic components, the coupling can provide a detailed analysis of coupled characteristics.

Figure 3. (a) Outlet coolant temperature and (b) Normalized pin power of HCF assembly

2.3.2. Coupling with MOOSE

A coupling method for coated particle fuel gas-cooled microreactors based on 3D MOC and Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) platform was developed (MOC/MOOSE). A mesh mapping method between constructive solid geometry with flat source region and finite element meshes was established. The MOC/MOOSE method was successfully applied to perform 3D full-core neutronics/thermal-hydraulic coupling calculations for a megawatt-level mixed-spectrum coated particle fuel gas-cooled microreactor with pin-wise resolution and high efficiency, obtaining power and temperature distributions throughout the entire lifetime.

Figure 4. (a) Power distribution of fuel power and (b) coolant temperature field of gas-cooled microreactor

3. CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive MC/MOC two-step analysis framework has been developed and demonstrated for high-fidelity neutronics and coupled multi-physics simulations of small and micro reactor cores. Continuous-energy Monte Carlo was employed to generate accurate multigroup cross sections through three distinct homogenization methods. Among them, the proposed TC-MHT method effectively incorporates both incident and outgoing anisotropies, significantly improving the accuracy of deterministic MOC calculations in fast and heterogeneous systems. The SPH correction, while less targeted at specific sources of error, remains a robust and engineering-friendly approach for thermal reactors.

Through extensive benchmark analyses, the MC/MOC two-step method achieved reactivity deviations within ± 200 pcm and pin-wise power RMS errors below 1% for multiple representative cores, validating its high predictive fidelity. The implementation of a GA-based optimization workflow provided an automated and quantitative strategy to tune MOC parameters, while GPU acceleration reduced computational time by up to 380 \times , allowing practical 3D full-core simulations on commodity hardware.

The framework was further extended to coupled analyses, including MOC/CTF for HCF assemblies and MOC/MOOSE for gas-cooled microreactors, demonstrating its flexibility for multi-physics integration. Overall, the developed MC/MOC methodology provides a unified, accurate, and computationally efficient tool for next-generation reactor core design and safety evaluation, particularly suited for complex geometries and compact heterogeneous systems.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Leppänen J, Pusa M, Fridman E. Overview of methodology for spatial homogenization in the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code[J]. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 2016, 96: 126 ~ 136.
- [2] Goorley T, James M, Booth T, Brown F, Bull J, Cox L J, Durkee J, Elson J, Fensin M, Forster R A, Hendricks J, Hughes H G, Johns R, Kiedrowski B, Martz R, Mashnik S, McKinney G, Pelowitz D, Prael R, Sweezy J, Waters L, Wilcox T, Zukaitis T. Taylor & Francis, 2012. Initial MCNP6 Release Overview[J]. *Nuclear Technology*, 2012, 180(3): 298 ~ 315.
- [3] Park H J, Shim H, Joo H, Kim C. Qualification test of few group constants generated from an MC method by the two-step neutronics analysis system McCARD/MASTER[J]. *undefined*, 2011.
- [4] Wang K, Li Z, She D, Liang J, Xu Q, Qiu Y, Yu J, Sun J, Fan X, Yu G. RMC – A Monte Carlo code for reactor core analysis[J]. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 2015, 82: 121 ~ 129.
- [5] Boyd W, Nelson A, Romano P K, Shaner S, Forget B, Smith K. Multigroup Cross-Section Generation with the OpenMC Monte Carlo Particle Transport Code[J]. *Nuclear Technology*, 2019, 205(7): 928 ~ 944.
- [6] Nguyen T D C, Lee H, Lee D. Use of Monte Carlo code MCS for multigroup cross section generation for fast reactor analysis[J]. *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, 2021, 53(9): 2788 ~ 2802.
- [7] Tran T Q, Cherezov A, Du X, Lee D. Verification of a two-step code system MCS/RAST-F to fast reactor core analysis[J]. *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, 2021, 54(5): 1789 ~ 1803.
- [8] Qin S, Li Y, He Q, Cao L, Wang Y, Wu Y, Wu H. Homogenized cross-section generation for pebble-bed type high-temperature gas-cooled reactor using NECP-MCX[J]. *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, 2023, 55(9): 3450 ~ 3463.

- [9] Kavenoky A. The SPH homogenization method[J]. , 1980.
- [10] Hébert A. CEA-N-2209, 1981. Développement de la méthode SPH: Homogénéisation de cellules dans un réseau non uniforme et calcul des paramètres de réflecteur[D]. , 1981.
- [11] Nikitin E, Fridman E, Mikityuk K. On the use of the SPH method in nodal diffusion analyses of SFR cores[J]. Annals of Nuclear Energy, 2015, 85: 544 ~ 551.
- [12] Guo H, Wu Y, Song Q, Cong T, Gu H. Development of OpenMC/Trivac two-step scheme for fast reactor core neutronics analysis[J]. Annals of Nuclear Energy, 2023, 190.
- [13] Wu Y, Song Q, Xu H, Hu J, Gu H, Guo H. Generation of multi-group cross-sections for microreactor with whole-core superhomogenization equivalence technique[C]/ICONE. , 2023Kyoto, Japan: .
- [14] Vidal J-F, Archier P, Calloo A, Jacquet P, Tommasi J. An improved energy-collapsing method for core-reflector modelization in sfr core calculations using the paris platform[C]/PHYSOR 2012. , 2012Knoxville, Tennessee, USA: : 15.
- [15] Vidal J-F, Archier P, Faure B, Jouault V, Palau J-M, Pascal V, Rimpault G, Auffret F, Graziano L, Masiello E, Santandrea S. APOLLO3® homogenization techniques for transport core calculations - application to the ASTRID CFV core[J]. Nuclear Engineering and Technology, 2017, 49: 1379 ~ 1387.
- [16] Wu Y, Song Q, Feng K, Vidal J-F, Gu H, Guo H. Multigroup cross-sections generated using Monte-Carlo method with flux-moment homogenization technique for fast reactor analysis[J]. Nuclear Engineering and Technology, 2023, 55: 2474 ~ 2482.
- [17] Shen Y, Wu Y, Song Q, Feng K, Guo H, Gu H. Transport-corrected flux-moment homogenization method for generating P0 multigroup cross-section based on continuous energy Monte-Carlo[J]. Annals of Nuclear Energy, 2025, 219: 111448.
- [18] Song Q, Zhang C, Wu Y, Feng K, Guo H, Gu H. Multi-objective optimization of method of characteristics parameters based on genetic algorithm[J]. Annals of Nuclear Energy, 2023, 194: 110096.
- [19] Feng K, Song Q, Shen Y, Lou L, Xiao Y, Guo H, Gu H. Development and verification of an MC/MOC two-step scheme for neutronic analysis of FCM-fueled micro gas-cooled reactor[J]. Annals of Nuclear Energy, 2025, 211: 110940.
- [20] Song Q, Wang R, Guo H, Gu H. MC/MOC two-step method for reactor physics analysis of helical cruciform fuel reactor[J]. Progress in Nuclear Energy, 2025, 180: 105607.